

Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Students' Learning Interest and Achievement in Economics in Public Senior Secondary Schools in the FCT Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of cooperative learning strategy on students' learning interest and achievement in economics concepts in public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study comprised of 22,320 SS2 students respectively in 96 Public Senior Secondary Schools. The sample for the study comprised of two intact classes with 138 SSII Students. The instrument used for data collection was a 40-item Economics Achievement Test (EAT). The test instrument was subjected to validation of experts in economics and Measurement and Evaluation. Scores emanating from the validation process was computed to obtain a logical validity index of 0.78. The instrument was further subjected to pilot study by administering it to a sample of 30 students within the study population but outside the sampled schools. Results obtained from the exercise were used to obtain reliability index of 0.77 for the achievement test respectively. The research was answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses was tested using t-test. The findings from the study showed there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy and conventional teaching strategy in public senior secondary schools in the FCT, Abuja and there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy in public senior secondary schools in the FCT, Abuja. The study recommended that teachers should be trained on the use of cooperative learning strategy and also economics teachers should be provided with appropriate and adequate learning materials that enhance effective use of cooperative learning strategy irrespective of gender. The study concluded that use cooperative learning strategy enhances students' achievement in the FCT, Abuja.

Keywords: Cooperative learning, Strategy, Students achievement, Economics, Public, Secondary schools.

Introduction

Economics is a vital subject offered at Senior Secondary School level in Nigeria. Economics is traced generally to the economic development of any nation. It is a social science of order, logic and pattern. Because we live in a world

of pattern where nothing is entirely new, anyone having very sound grasp of the knowledge of economics may not find it difficult to fit in, since everything about Economics itself is pattern. It has been reported by several scholars in education that good knowledge of economics will help students understand other subjects. Akinoso, Olafare, and Akinoso (2021) averred that any student who does not understand Economics well will end up struggling in other subjects and such students' career options are limited. Elaine (2021) while defining economics as the social science that studies with the production, distribution and consumption of goods and services. Adewale and Anaduaka (2018) submitted that economics is a logical way of thinking that aims at solving personal and social problems; and it has timely improved business, production and recreational activities. The concern of stake holders in the education industry is that in spite of the importance of Economics to the society, students are not performing satisfactorily well in both internal and external examinations. WAEC Economics result analysis in Nigeria from 2016-2020 revealed that 487,835 (31.58%), 443,426 (28.44%), 635,930 (40.78%), 569,570 (35.82) and 534,756 (34.76%) could not pass Economics at credit level in 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 respectively. These numbers of non-credit performance are considered too high by the researchers and it calls for concern. Academic achievement refers to how students manage their learning and how they cope with or accomplish various tasks assigned by their teachers. Academic achievement is the ability to study and remember facts and to be able to communicate facts and knowledge orally or on paper. Adeniyi and Aderinkola (2023) reports that in educational institutions, success is measured by academic achievement or the extent to which a student meets the standards set by the institution.

Moreover, negative feelings towards learning of economics begin as a result of a number of encounters relating to the way economics teachers present or teach the subject to the students. Because of the importance placed on economics, the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013), apart from making economics a core subject in both primary and Secondary schools also demand that in order to fully achieve the goals of education in Nigeria and gain from its contribution to the national economy, government shall take necessary measures to ensure that teaching shall be practical, activity-based, experimental, socially interactive and Information Technology (IT) supported. One of the social interactive strategies of teaching economics today which may also significantly enhance achievement, increase students' interest and reduce anxiety of young learners is the cooperative Learning Strategy. Cooperative learning (CL) is described by Cornelius-Ukpepi et al. (2016), as 'an instructional method in which students work together in small groups in order to facilitate effective learning. Cooperative strategy is an educational strategy to learning that brings together groups of learners in the same level of education (class) to solve a problem, finish a task, or craft and an invention (Cornelius-Ukpepi et al., 2016). In the cooperative learning, the learners are challenged both socially and emotionally as they listen to different perspectives, and are required to articulate and defend their ideas. A series of empirical reviews have been carried by authors on the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic achievement.

Kaymak et al. (2022) investigated the effect of Cooperative Learning (CL) on 8th grade students' academic achievement while also considering the achievement outcomes by gender and to test the hypothesis that CL improves student achievement. The present study was carried out during the Covid-19 pandemic for six weeks during the academic year 2020-2021 in Nurorda high-school in Nursultan in Kazakhstan. The subjects of the study were 86

students (31 girls and 55 boys) aged 13-15 years old and were randomly divided into two groups, 45 students in the experimental group and 41 students in the control group. Final test was administered to students as measuring instrument. The t-test statistical technique was performed in order to answer to the research questions. The data obtained were analysed with SPSS 21.00 statistical program. The significance level was taken as $p < 0.05$ in the analyses. Results indicated that the CL has significant positive effects on students' mathematics achievement. Keywords: cooperative learning, mathematics achievement, gender differences.

Obasi (2023) investigated the effect of cooperative learning strategy on students' academic achievement in Economics in public secondary schools in Imo State. The study was guided by two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses. The study used a quasi-experimental design, namely a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent, control group, quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was made up of 94,412 students enrolled in 296 secondary schools throughout the 6 education zones in Imo State. Purposive and cluster sampling approaches were adopted to select 97 senior secondary two students from two coeducational institutions. The Economics Achievement Test (EAT), which consisted of fifty (50) multiple choice objective, was used to collect data. Using Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R20). A reliability coefficient of 0.85 was achieved. The research questions were answered through mean scores and standard deviation statistics whereas the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Students who were taught Economics through a cooperative learning strategy performed much better than students who were taught Economics through a lecture method. In the post-test only, the results demonstrated that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students who were taught Economics utilizing a cooperative learning technique. Based on the findings, it was suggested, among other things, that students in large classrooms should be divided into smaller groups so that they can participate in discussions and then present their findings in class.

Moreover, the trend in student achievement in FCT in recent times has been worrisome to researchers, the government and other stakeholders in the secondary school system within FCT, Abuja. The use of crude teaching methods to facilitate the teaching and learning of economics has weakened the capacity of teachers to effectively transmit knowledge to learners in a manner that would enhance their academic achievement. The teaching and learning of economics require the use of teaching strategies that are student centered such as cooperative learning strategy. The aim of teaching in any educational system is to promote a permanent change in behaviour. Furthermore, attention should be given to gender differences that may exist in terms of learners' achievement. Meaningful learning according to Borich (2011) is an important factor that can be achieved when teachers adapt instruction to meet male and female students varied academic needs irrespective of their gender. Gender is the sexual assignment or identity of an individual. The influence of gender and its interaction with instructional strategies have remained inconclusive. Studies had shown that certain instructional methods favour males more than females and others reported otherwise. Effective instructional strategies however, must have the potency to positively enhance achievement irrespective of students' gender. This study is therefore geared towards examining the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic achievement in mathematics in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What difference exist in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja?
2. What difference exist in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy in public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided this study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy in public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja.

Theoretical Framework

Social interdependence theory is adopted for this study. The theory was propounded by David W Johnson and Roger T Johnson, two American Educational Psychologists in the 1970s. The social I interdependence theory explains how social relationships and interactions, influence motivation, behavior and learning outcomes. The social interdependence theory promotes positive interdependence by ensuring that individuals work together to achieve a common goal, promoting mutual support. The theory further emphasizes on individual accountability, promote interaction and social skills. The theory is relevant to the current research work because it encourages students to collaborate and work in groups in groups complete tasks, promoting mutual support, shared knowledge and collective responsibility.

Research Method

Quasi-experimental research design was used in this study. The population of the study comprises 22,320 SS2 students respectively in 96 Public Senior Secondary Schools. The sample for the study comprised of two intact classes with 138 SSII Students. The instrument used for data collection was a 40-item Economics Achievement Test was developed for the study for the purpose assessing students' academic achievement in economics. The instrument was further subjected to pilot study. The instruments were pilot tested on 30 students; the respondents were part of the population but not part of the sample for this study. The data obtained from the pilot test was used to compute the internal consistency of the instrument using Kuder Richardson reliability method. Results obtained from

the exercise were used to obtain reliability index of 0.77 for the Economics Achievement Test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions developed for the study while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What difference exists in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with collaborative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja

Table 1. Mean and Standard Showing Difference in the Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Economics with Collaborative Learning Strategy and those taught with Conventional Learning Strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

S/N	Groups	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Achievement Gain
			Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	
1	Experimental	75	35.29	7.71	53.25	9.73	17.96
2	Control	63	20.71	3.24	27.87	3.17	7.16

Table 1 shows the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with collaborative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. Results indicate that the pretest mean and standard deviation interest scores for the experimental group was given as 35.29 and 7.71 respectively while the posttest mean and standard deviation scores were 53.25 and 9.73. As for the control group, the pretest mean and standard deviation interest scores were 20.71 and 3.24 respectively while the posttest mean and standard deviation mean scores were given 27.87 and 3.17 respectively. It is observed from the table that the mean gain for the experimental group was found to be higher at 17.96 than the mean achievement gain of the control group at 7.16. Hence difference exists a high difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with collaborative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja.

Research Questions 2: What difference exist in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of the FCT, Abuja?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Showing extent of difference in Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught Economics using Cooperative Learning Technology in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

S/N	Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Achievement Gain
			Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	
1	Male	76	17.00	2.79	67.75	8.40	50.75
2	Female	62	12.29	4.59	40.00	2.45	27.71

Table 2 shows the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy differ in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. Results indicate that the pretest mean and standard deviation academic achievement scores for the male learners was given as 17.00 and 2.79 respectively while the posttest mean and standard deviation scores were 67.75 and 8.40. As for female learners, the pretest mean and standard deviation academic achievement scores were 12.29 and 4.59 respectively while the posttest mean and standard deviation mean scores were given 40.00 and 2.45 respectively. It is observed from the table that the mean gain for the male students was found to be higher at 50.75 than the mean achievement gain of the female students at 27.71 Hence, mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy differ to a high extent in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. Hence, male students achieved better than their female counterparts.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja

Table 3. Analysis of Variance Showing Significant of Difference in the Mean Achievement Scores of Students Taught Economics with Cooperative Learning Strategy and those taught with Conventional Learning Strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

Source	Type III Sum of				
	Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	288.741 ^a	2	144.371	4.675	.036
Intercept	1738.243	1	1738.243	28.142	.000
Pre-test Strategies	460.546	1	460.546	3.774	.000
Error	288.741	1	288.741	4.675	.036
Total	2841.259	72	39.462	7.317	.000
	67078.000	75			

Corrected Total	3130.000	74
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Table 3 above shows analysis of variance on the significance of difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja.

The results showed that at F-calculated value of 4.675, the p-value of 0.036 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in mean achievement Scores of male and female students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

Table 4. Analysis of variance Statistics showing the Significance of difference in Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught Economics using Cooperative Learning Strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	472.580 ^a	2	236.290	48.123	.000
Intercept	198.138	1	198.138	20.176	.000
pretest	43.123	1	43.123	4.595	.000
Gender	472.580	1	472.580	48.124	.000
Error	451.733	72	9.820		
Total	37721.000	75			
Corrected Total	924.312	74			

Table 4 above shows the analysis of variance statistic on the significance of difference in Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught economics using cooperative Learning strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja. The results showed that at F-calculated value of 48.123, the p-value of 0.000 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals that there is a significant difference in mean achievement Scores of male and female students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja.

Discussion

Findings from the study on hypothesis one reveal there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. This finding is in agreement with the findings from the study of Obasi (2023) showed significant effect of cooperative learning strategy on students' academic achievement in Economics in public secondary schools in Imo State. Furthermore, the study of Jekayinfa, Durojaiye & Oloda, (2023) indicated there significant effect of cooperative learning strategy (CLS) on senior secondary school students' anxiety and achievement in geometrical construction (GC) in Abuja. This entails that employing the use of cooperative learning strategy enhances students' academic achievement.

Findings from the study on hypothesis two reveal there is a significant difference in mean achievement Scores of male and female students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy in Public Senior Secondary Schools of FCT, Abuja. This finding is in agreement with the findings from the study of Kaymak et al (2022) which indicated significant effect of Cooperative Learning (CL) on 8th grade students' academic achievement while also considering the achievement outcomes by gender. This entails that employing cooperative learning strategies in the course of instructional delivery helps in affects male and female students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught economics with cooperative learning strategy and those taught with conventional learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. Results further reveal that there is a significant difference in mean achievement Scores of male and female students taught economics using cooperative learning strategy in public senior secondary schools of FCT, Abuja. Based on these results, it was therefore recommended among others that schools should be equipped by the Federal ministry of Education with cooperative learning tools for the purpose of creating an enabling environment that will enhance students' learning interest. Additionally, Economics teachers should be provided with appropriate and adequate learning materials that can enhance irrespective of gender.

References

- Adeniyi, A.A and Aderinkola, D (2023) The effect of virtual learning on students' academic performance in mathematics in post Covid-19 era. *AJSTME*, Vol. 8, Special Issue No. 1, 456-462, August, 2022.
<https://www.ajstme.com.ng>
- Adewale Olanrewaju, Sunday & Anaduaka, Uche. (2018). effect of think-pair-share cooperative strategy on mathematics achievement of attention-deficit hyperactive students. 43. 41-50.
- Akinoso, S.O. Olafare, F.O and Akinoso, O.B (2021). Effect of Collaborative Teaching on Secondary School Students' Achievement in and Attitude towards Mathematics.
<https://doi.org/10.51584/ijrias.2021.6801>

Borich, G.D (2011) Effective Teaching Methods. U.K: Institute of Technology Press.

Cornelius-Ukpepi, B.U., Aglazor, G.N. & Odey, C.O. (2016). Cooperative Learning Strategy as Tool for Classroom Management. *Advances in Multidisciplinary and Scientific Research*. Vol.2, No2, 67-75.

Elaine J. H (2021) What is mathematics? <https://www.livescience.com/38936-mathematics.html>

Jekayinfa, O. J., Durojaiye, D.S. and Oloda, F.S. S. (2023). Effect of Collaborative Learning Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students' Anxiety and Achievement in Geometrical Construction in Abuja. *British journal of multidisciplinary and advanced studies*. Vol. 4, No. 3.

Kaymak, Serkan & Kassymbek, Zh & Aliyeva, Kalamkas & Saydenov, F. (2022). The Effect of Cooperative Learning on Students Academic Achievement. *Achievement. Journal of Management Studies* 9(6):495-503. Vol. 7 No. 2

National Education Policy (2013). Downloaded at National Education Policy 2013 | PDF

Obasi, H (2023). The Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on students' Academic Achievement in Economics in public secondary schools in Imo State *Serkan. South Eastern Journal of Sustainable Development*. Vol. 7(2); 200-211.

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